

WAVELET IMAGE PROCESSING FOR WEAR AND EROSION MAPPING USING AN ULTRASONIC GAUGING TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

A wavelet transform image decomposition technique was developed for compression and analysis of the ultrasonic images resulting in a great decrease in time and resources. The data is generated by a Computerized Ultrasonic Gauging System (CUGS) recently developed which using time delay measurements generates very precise topographical maps of the outer and inner surfaces of tubes during the various stages of manufacture. The dimensions of the part are displayed as images. The wavelet technique here presented is utilized to evaluate wear and erosion patterns measured before and after exposure to environments involving extreme temperature, pressure, corrosive gases and mechanical forces.

INTRODUCTION

A Computerized Ultrasonic Gauging System (CUGS) has been developed to generate very precise topographical maps of the outer and inner surfaces of tubes during various stages of manufacture and life-cycle of the parts. Measurements of the tube dimensions are obtained with a resolution of $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (10^{-4} inches) and accuracies of the order of $10 \mu\text{m}$ (4×10^{-4} inches) or better. A typical output of CUGS is an ultrasonic image, in which the horizontal and vertical axes represent the axial and angular position of the part, respectively[1]. The cylindrical coordinate system (r, ϕ, z) used to describe the part, is represented as a color image in which the column represents the position z along the axis of the tube, the row represents the angular position ϕ , and the color of the pixel represents the radius r . The colors are linearly mapped to the physical dimensions of the I.D. or O.D. radius. For example, a point on the surface with cylindrical coordinates $(r=3, \phi=72, z=20)$ is represented in the image as a point P in row 20 and column 72, with a color equivalent to the value 3. All data points measured at the same z value, but at various angles ϕ , are represented as a column of the image.

A common problem of imaging systems is the storage and handling of a large quantity of data acquired. CUGS is currently utilized to gauge tubes as long as 7.5 m (25 feet) resulting in the acquisition of more than 5,000,000 data points, which require up to 40 Mbytes of disk memory on a computer.

A Wavelet Transform Image decomposition technique was thus developed for compression and processing of the ultrasonic images, resulting in a great decrease in time and resources needed to perform such operations. Wavelet-based image analysis has two distinct characteristics: multiresolution and high spatial

localization[2]. An important feature of this techniques is the successive approximation property: as more details, i.e. higher spatial frequency components, are added, higher resolution images are obtained. As the image is displayed at various resolutions, it is possible to enhance or diminish contributions from different physical atoms within the image. At a lower resolution it is possible to determine properties of larger structures such as erosion patterns or gouges, while at finer resolutions it is possible to enhance details such as pits or ridges. In the application here discussed, wavelet decomposition of the ultrasonic images is utilized to map the wear of the internal surface of steel tubes, before and after exposure to extreme environments involving temperature, pressure, corrosive gases and mechanical forces, but results can be utilized in many applications, including document and medical imaging, remote sensing, teleconferencing and facsimile and data transmission.

MULTIRESOLUTION ANALYSIS OF IMAGES

Due to the large size of the data file a representation of the data which can reduce the storage space, but mainly reduce the access, handling and display times is needed. For example, mapping of the inside surface of a tube can result in an image which has $500 \times 10,000$ points with a memory occupancy of over 40 Mbytes, and the time needed to display this data is significant.

One possible approach to reduce this bottleneck in the performance of the visualization of ultrasonic images is the so-called multiresolution visualization. The principle of this technique is to utilize the least amount of data necessary to generate an usable approximation of the original data. The data is analyzed at different scales of resolution in which the higher scales present more details than the lower scales. This representation is thus used to reduce the size of the data to be visualized and thus the associated computational load. For example, if it is necessary to look at the tube in all its length, which is usually of the order of 5-10 meters, it will not be useful to display features of the order of 1 mm. As the user requires further refinements, i.e. zooms into a specified area of the tube, more data are loaded into memory and a higher resolution image is reconstructed and displayed. This is an equivalent process to the one performed by a microscope, in which the resolution is changed by looking at different scales of the image. This concept is very well understood and utilized by cartographers when designing and reproducing maps[3].

Burt and Adelson have introduced a fast pyramidal

Figure 1. Block diagram of the filter bank performing a single level of the wavelet decomposition.

implementation for computing the image details at different resolutions using subband coding, and have shown that multiresolution representations are very effective for analyzing the information content of images[4]. Following this approach, Mallat has proposed a scheme for the decomposition of signals and images using an orthogonal multiresolution representation called the wavelet transform representation[5]. A block diagram of this technique is shown in Figure 1, where the input image A^{j-1} (j being the level) is processed and subsampled by the filter bank in figure. Each row of the image is processed as a one-dimensional sequence $x(n)$ using two filters, an high pass and a low pass finite impulse response filters, $h(n)$ and $g(n)$ respectively. Because of the bandwidth reduction after filtering, and of particular conditions set on $h(n)$ and $g(n)$, the resultant outputs of the filters can be downsampled by a factor 2, i.e. every other point of the sequence is discarded[6]. The output of $h(n)$ will thus be a sequence half in length ($N/2$) which contains the higher frequency components of $x(n)$ while the output of $g(n)$ will contain the lower frequency components. This process is repeated for each row, and two sub-images of N rows and $N/2$ columns are obtained as output. An identical analysis is now performed on the columns using the same filters. The ultrasonic image A^{j-1} (size $N \times N$) is thus decomposed into a series of 4 sub-images of size $N/2 \times N/2$. One of the sub-images (A^j) represents a "coarser" approximation of the input image A^{j-1} since it contains only the lower frequency components of both the row and column sequences and the other three represent the higher resolution "details" (D_1^j, D_2^j, D_3^j). A^j can also be used recursively as the input to the filter bank. The inverse transformation, i.e. the inverse wavelet transform, is obtained using the same orthonormal filters[6]. A graphical depiction of the output of the Discrete Wavelet Transform filter bank is displayed in Figure 2. After the first level of decomposition ($j=1$) the image A^0 has been divided into 4 sub-images A^1, D_1^1, D_2^1, D_3^1 . The sub-image A^1 represents the coarser representation of the original image, and the details to the image are added as the other sub-images $D_1^1,$

D_2^1, D_3^1 are also utilized. It needs to point out that A^1 still represents the same area as A^0 , the difference being that the spatial resolution is less for the former, and thus half of the points are needed to represent the part.

After 3 iterations the original image A^0 of size $N \times N$ has been decomposed into a series of 10 sub-images of varying dimensions (Figure 2). The sub-images A^3, D_1^3, D_2^3, D_3^3 have size ($N/8 \times N/8$) while D_1^2, D_2^2, D_3^2 have size ($N/4 \times N/4$) and D_1^1, D_2^1, D_3^1 have size ($N/2 \times N/2$). The total number of data points is still ($N \times N$), i.e. the same as the original image.

From this decomposition different representation of the image can be obtained, from a coarse approximation with A^3 (of size $N/8 \times N/8$) to the full resolution with A^0 ($N \times N$). Instead of viewing the image at full resolution the user can select the level of expansion required; the details to the image are added as the other sub-images (D_k) are utilized with an increase in dimensions. The data is thus stored as a series of sub-images, and it can be visualized at different resolutions. At the lowest resolution the whole tube is displayed, and as the user "zooms in", the resolution is increased by adding the detail information, but a reduced fraction of the tube is now displayed. For example, if the resolution is doubled only half of the length of the tube will be displayed. A summary of the size of the image as a function of the resolution is given in Table I. For comparison the original image size necessary to cover the same length of the tube is also given in the Table.

WAVELET COMPRESSION/DECOMPRESSION OF ULTRASONIC IMAGES

The original ultrasonic image is thus processed using a Forward Wavelet Transform composed of a sequence of three filter banks of Figure 1. The output is an image of size $N \times N$ which has identical information content of the original image, nothing is lost and perfect reconstruction is achieved. The reconstruction error is only due to the numerical precision of the

Figure 2. Display of the wavelet transform of the filter bank Figure 1 iterated 3 times.

Figure 3. Block diagram of the wavelet image processing technique described in the text.

filters utilized: in our implementation using MATLAB on a Silicon Graphics Indigo² Workstation, the maximum error of reconstruction is of 8×10^{-11} in.

From wavelet theory, it can be shown that it is not necessary to retain all the $N \times N$ coefficients of the wavelet transformed images. By thresholding the wavelet image, the number of coefficients needed to visualize the data is reduced, resulting in a reduction of the memory space necessary to store the ultrasonic images[7]. The output image can be thresholded to reduce the amount of data necessary to represent the part. To retrieve the image the inverse wavelet transform is performed to the resolution needed. The schematic representation of the wavelet technique here presented is shown in Figure 3. The original image is transformed using the forward wavelet transform (FWT) and the output is a wavelet image similar to the image shown in the bottom left of Figure 2. This image is thus thresholded in order to reduce the amount of coefficients, obtaining a compressed image which is saved to disk using Hauffman coding. To retrieve the image, after Hauffman decoding, the inverse wavelet transform (IWT) is performed. The level of reconstruction will depend on the resolution needed to visualize the data, as discussed previously.

Thresholding does introduce an error since the smallest coefficients are eliminated and set to zero. In order to properly quantify the procedure here described, two quantities were calculated as a function of the threshold level: (1) maximum error in reconstruction, i.e. the maximum difference in absolute value between the original image and the 1:1 resolution processed image, calculated at each pixel; (2) compression ratio (CR), i.e. the ratio of the size of the file of the original image and the size of the file of the compressed image. These two quantities were calculated as a function of the threshold and results are shown in Figure 4. In the top plot the reconstruction error is plotted, while the relative compression ratios are given in the bottom plot. The threshold is defined between 0 and 1, where 1 refers in the case

Table I. Summary of required sizes and dimensions as a function of the image resolution

Resolution	Image Size Displayed	Original Size
1:8	64 x 1408	512 x 11264
1:4	128 x 1408	512 x 5632
1:2	256 x 1280	512 x 2560
1:1	512 x 1024	512 x 1024

in which all the values of the image are set to zero, i.e. 100% thresholding. If the threshold is set to 0.6, 60% of the values of the wavelet image are set to zero.

The upper limit of the acceptable error is 0.0004 inches, which corresponds to a threshold of 0.6. From the bottom plot, this corresponds to a CR of 3.6, meaning that from an original file size of 40 Mbytes, we now require only 12 Mbytes. Higher compression ratios are usually presented in image processing literature since it is common practice to utilize the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), also plotted in the top plot of Figure 5. Using this error definition, the threshold can be set to 0.75, resulting in a CR of 4.7 and thus a file size of 8.5 Mbytes. Unfortunately, the RMSE is not a practical measure of the quality of the compression algorithm, since in our application, the ultrasonic images are utilized for precise gauging, thus no pixel can be represented with an absolute error larger than 0.0004 inches.

Figure 4. Plot of the maximum error of reconstruction (top) and the compression ratio (bottom) as a function of the threshold.

Figure 5. Ultrasonic image of a rifled tube showing erosion in some areas.

EROSION PATTERN ENHANCEMENT

Other benefits of thresholding are to reduce noise in the image[8]and/or to enhance particular features. Wavelet Transform has been utilized for feature enhancement and extraction with promising results in many applications[9]. The basic approach of image feature enhancement is given by these simple steps: (1) Image decomposition with the Forward wavelet Transform; (2) Linear or non-linear processing of the wavelet coefficients; and (3) image reconstruction with the Inverse Wavelet Transform.

Many tubes mapped using CUGS are internally rifled, i.e. they exhibit a periodic variation in the internal radius image. An image of one of these tubes is given in Figure 5. In this case an erosion pattern is visible by following the two lighter lines which transverse obliquely across the image. Wavelet analysis can be used to separate the different contributions of rifling and erosion from the image. By selectively setting to zero all the coefficients in the sub-images which mainly contain information about the rifling, the erosion pattern is enhanced in the reconstructed image, as shown in Figure 6. In this image the variation in dimensions due to rifling is completely lost, in fact the difference between this image and the one in Figure 5 represents the original rifling dimensions before erosion did occur.

CONCLUSIONS

A novel approach to analyze and display ultrasonic images obtained using a Computerized Ultrasonic Gauging System was presented. The Multiresolution technique employed permits the display of the data at different resolutions with a great decrease in time and resources needed to perform such operations. The wavelet technique was also extended to enhance features such as erosion patterns in rifled steel tubes.

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Figure 6. Reconstructed image showing enhancement of the erosion pattern.